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OSTEO NS 2021

Institute for Rehabilitation, Belgrade

FRACTURE CONSOLIDATION IN PATIENTS WITH REDUCED BONE DENSITY

KONSOLIDACIJA PRELOMA KOD PACIJENATA SA SMANJENOM GUSTINOM KOSTIJU

Olivera ILIĆ STOJANOVIĆ

Summary

Introduction. The strategy of choosing drug therapy for patients with new low-energy fractures, is still ongoing discussed topic, particular problem and challenge for clinicians. **Material and Methods.** Analytic research method according to the PubMed relevant publications in the last 20 years. **Results.** It is considered that aging and osteoporosis are not correlated with the values of trabecular bone volume and the outcome of the operation. Elderly and osteoporotic patients with increased metabolic activity have a better outcome of osteosynthetic vertebral fusion and benefit the healing process. The patients with lower metabolic turnover, higher bone mineral density, and volume have worse results. The impaired ability of good fixation of osteosynthetic material due to the both thinned cortical layer and trabecular structure has been proven in rare publications. The lack of prospective clinical data studies, a shorter period of fracture repair in animal models, where the extrapolation of results is not safe, significantly complicates response accuracy. Elderly patients have lower trabecular density, lower volume and bone mineral density, higher intertrabecular space, but not a worse operative outcome compared to the age of 40-50. **Conclusion.** Therefore, osteoporosis may not in itself be a significant risk factor for an operative outcome or at least not to the expected extent. Contradictory, opinions regarding the effects of drug therapy primarily bisphosphonates, which are very often prescribed, indicate that the experience of clinicians and detailed individual approach of patients is crucial in the strategy of treating fractures in people with reduced bone density.

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad¹
Health Center Novi Sad, Novi Sad²
Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases, Novi Sad³

THE ASSOCIATION OF EARLY MENOPAUSE AND OSTEOPOROTIC HIP FRACTURES

POVEZANOST RANE MENOPAUZE I PRELOMA KUKA KAO POSLEDICE OSTEOPOROZE

Ivana MINAKOVIĆ^{1,2}, Ksenija BOŠKOVIĆ^{1,3} and Jelena ZVEKIĆ SVORCAN^{1,3}

Summary

Introduction. Postmenopausal osteoporosis is a frequent disease that increases fracture risk and represents a major public health problem. The aim of this study was to assess the impact of early menopause on the occurrence of hip fractures. **Material and Methods.** The retrospective cross-sectional study included 200 postmenopausal women aged ≥ 50 years who underwent bone mineral densitometry at the Special Hospital for Rheumatic Diseases Novi Sad, Serbia during 2015–2018. Patients were divided into two groups, the first group (N=107) was composed of women with spontaneous early menopause at the age of 40–45, and the second group (N=93) consisted of women in whom menopause occurred after age 45. The FRAX score for the Serbian population was calculated for each respondent. Women who have used hormone replacement therapy were excluded. **Results.** The groups were uniform by age and body mass index ($p > 0.005$), while the first group had a lower bone mineral density of the femoral neck (Me = 0.78 vs. Me = 0.86), $p < 0.001$. Respondents with early menopause had higher FRAX scores (higher risk) for hip fractures (Me 1.80) compared to women with menopause after the age of 45 (1.10), $p = 0.001$. Respondents with early menopause were more likely to have a high ten-year risk for hip fracture (32.2%) compared to women with menopause after the age of 45 (8.6%), $p < 0.001$. **Conclusion.** Our results suggest that early menopause could contribute to predicting future fractures.

OsteoNS 2021.

1ST ANNUAL INTERNATIONAL MEETING
ON MUSCULOSKELETAL DISEASES - OSTEOARTROSIS,
OSTEOPOROSIS AND SARCOPENIA

Novi Sad, Serbia

19 - 21.11.2021.

OsteoNS 2021.**1st International (Hybrid) Meeting on Musculoskeletal Diseases
- Osteoarthritis, Osteoporosis and Sarcopenia**

19.11.2021.		
12:00 - 13:00	Registracija učesnika	
12:30 - 13:30	Ručak	
13:40 - 14:00	Svečano otvaranje	
14:00	OSTEOARTROZE I - predsedavajući R. Matijević, V. Harhaji	
14:00 - 14:25	Revisiting the Hipocratic Oath Simulation, visualisation and artheficial intelligence in the era of precision medicine	Li Felländer - Tsai, EFORT president
14:25 - 14:50	Osteoporozna iz aspekta primarne zdravstvene zaštite	Veselin Bojat, direktor DZ Novi Sad
14:50 - 15:10	Management of knee osteoarthritis: from the ESCEO algorithm to a multidisciplinary multicomponent patient - centred approach	Jean Yves Reginster, ESCEO president
15:10 - 15:20	Diskusija	
15:20 - 15:50	Sponzorisan predavanje MV Pharm	
15:50 - 16:10	Kafe pauza	
16:10	OSTEOARTROZE II - predsedavajući M. Milankov	
16:10 - 16:40	Sponzorisan predavanje Vemax Pharma	
16:40 - 17:00	Physical activity in osteoarthritis threatment	Olivier Bruyere, Liege University
17:00 - 17:20	Intraartikularno lečenje osteoartritisa pod kontrolom UZ	Nemanja Damjanov, Beograd
17:20 - 17:40	Operativno lečenje osteoartroza	Dragan Savić, KOHIT KCV
17:40 - 18:00	Razvoj digitalnih tehnologija u oblasti medicine tokom Covid epidemije	Nemanja Kovačev, Syrmia/ Istraživačko - razvojni institut RT - RK za sisteme zasnovane na računarima
18:00 - 18:10	Diskusija	
18:10 - 18:40	Sponzorisan predavanje Aleksandar MN	
21:00	Svečana večera	
20.11.2021.		
08:40	SARKOPENIJA i OSTEOPOROZA I - predsedavajući S.Tomašević - Todorović	
08:40 - 08:50	Results of hip prosthesis implantation in patients on dialysis with osteoporosis	Vladimir Ristić, Opšta bolnica Subotica
08:50 - 09:00	The association of early menopause and osteoporotic hip fractures	Ivana Minaković, Dom zdravlja Novi Sad
09:00 - 09:10	Stiff knee after arthroplasty - issues in rehabilitation practice	Tatjana Nožica - Radulović, Zavod "Dr Miroslav Zotović" Banja Luka
09:10 - 09:30	A national survey on AI in radiology and potential of AI in osteoporosis prediction	Ivo Dumić - Čule University North, Varaždin
09:30 - 09:50	Importance of sarcopenia	Alfonso Cruz - Jentof, Universidad Europea de Madrid
09:50 - 10:10	SARC - F role in diagnosing sarcopenia	Gulistan Bahat, Istanbul University
10:10 - 10:30	FRAX	Eugen McCloskey, Sheffield University

10:30 - 10:50	Značaj i uloga TBS - a u dijagnozi osteoporozne i u kliničkoj praksi	Jelena Aleksić, ŽTP Beograd
10:50 - 11:10	Vitamin D supplementation: upper limit for safety revisited	Rene Rizzoli, Geneva University
11:10 - 11:30	Closing the Treatment Gap	Cyrus Cooper, IOF president
11:30 - 11:50	Kafe pauza	
11:50	SARKOPENIJA i OSTEOPOROZA II - predsedavajući O. Dulić	
11:50 - 12:10	Secondary fracture prevention	Kassim Javaid, Oxford University
12:10 - 12:25	Uticaj magnetoterapije na koštani deficit	Tamara Popović, Zavod "Dr Miroslav Zotović", Banja Luka
12:25 - 12:45	Operativno lečenje osteoporotskih preloma kuka	Vladimir Harhaji, Ortho MD Novi Sad
12:45 - 13:00	SarQoL Serbia	Radmila Matijević, KOHIT KCV
13:00 - 13:15	Rehabilitacija nakon osteoporotskih preloma	Snežana Tomašević - Todorović, Klinika za medicinsku rehabilitaciju KCV
13:15 - 13:45	Sponzorisan predavanje Amicus	
14:00 - 15:00	Ručak	
15:00	OSTEOARTROZE III - predsedavajući D. Savić	
15:00 - 15:30	Sponzorisan predavanje Viatrix	
15:30 - 15:50	Mogućnosti hirurškog lečenja osteoartroze kolena	Marko Kadija, KCS Beograd
15:50 - 16:10	Halux valgus	Predrag Rašović, KOHIT KCV
16:10 - 16:30	Klinička efikasnost regenerativnih preparata u lečenju osteoartritisa kolena	Oliver Dulić, KOHIT KCV
16:30 - 16:50	Degenerativne promene zgloba kolena nakon povrede prednjeg ukrštenog ligamenta	Miroslav Milankov, KOHIT KCV
16:50 - 17:10	Rehabilitacija pacijenata sa osteoartrozom	Ksenija Bošković, Specijalna bolnica za reumatske bolesti Novi Sad
17:10 - 17:20	Diskusija	
21.11.2021.		
08:40	PRELOMI - predsedavajući M. Stanković	
08:40 - 08:55	Our complications of arthroscopic knee surgery in local anesthesia	Milan Milović, Opšta bolnica Vrbas
08:55 - 9:10	Fracture consolidation in patients with reduced bone density	Olivera Ilić - Stojanović, Institut za rehabilitaciju, Beograd
09:10 - 09:30	Operativno lečenje osteoporotskih preloma kičmenih pršljenova	Nemanja Gvozdenović, KOHIT KCV
09:30 - 09:50	Rehabilitacija spinalnih lezija dinamičkim exoskeletnim sistemom (Hybrid Assistive limb HAL - CYBERDYNE)	Dušan Marić, Ortho MD Novi Sad
09:50 - 10:10	Operativno lečenje osteoporotskih preloma proximalnog humerusa	Srdan Ninković, KOHIT KCV
10:10 - 10:25	Operativno lečenje osteoporotskih preloma zgloba lakta	Mirko Obradović, KOHIT KCV
10:25 - 10:40	Operativno lečenje osteoporotskih preloma ručnog zgloba	Miodrag Vranješ, KOHIT KCV
10:40 - 10:55	Uslovna modulacija bola - klinička primena?	Aleksandar Knežević, Klinika za med. rehabilitaciju KCV
11:00	Diskusija; Završna reč i zatvaranje simpozijuma	